

Together,
there's
something
science
can do.

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Issue/problem

Canada's research ecosystem faces tension between maintaining scientific collaboration and ensuring research security to prevent foreign interference. [The Council of Canadian Academies](#) (CCA) investigated this issue.

Description of the problem

Canada's collaborative research model is vulnerable to exploitation by state and non-state actors. Open science promotes transparency, reproducibility, and accessibility, but may conflict with security imperatives given Canada's fragmented policy landscape, reduced security capacity for smaller institutions, and inadequate communication between national agencies and institutions.

Results

The CCA recommends adopting a five-point policy framework:

1. **Support for knowledge-sharing:** The establishment of specialized centres that provide advice and facilitate collaboration nationally to address fragmentation and align domestic approaches with international partners.
2. **Capacity-building:** Training to inform researchers of their responsibilities and boost capacity about research security are necessary.
3. **Guaranteeing sustainable funding for research security:** Sustaining funding is required to support research on national security, to be distributed equitably between large and smaller institutions.
4. **Implementing compliance enforcement measures:** Adherence to stricter research security measures can be best achieved through restrictions on access to funding sources and competitions for non-compliant actors.
5. **Fostering a 'modern research' mindset:** Normative training for researchers and actors within the research sector to ensure that all actors are aware of their role and the importance of research security.

Lessons learned

The CCA suggests that research security will become increasingly important as economic tensions continue to inform international relations. Continued monitoring will be necessary to ensure that innovation and security are adequately addressed.